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IDENTIFYING FACTORS AND CONDITIONS OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY DESIGN TEAM IN AN EDUCATIONAL SETTING

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ABSTRACT

Business schools and Engineering colleges are seeking to work with Design schools to forge new interdisciplinary programs (Lockwood, 2010).

Multidisciplinary Design Education plays an essential role in such programs. Seoul National University's Design department, Engineering College, and Business school began its Integrated Creative Design Education Program in 2009. Two years of education management has revealed the necessity of developing implementable multidisciplinary design education.

This paper studies multidisciplinary design education cases to identify its factors and conditions, and to analyze the causes of such behavior. The final aim is to find blueprint for multidisciplinary design education model. As an outcome, four main categories have been drawn out: project theme and attribution, composition of project team members, project development process, and knowledge resource management. Then causal relation between these categories are identified. The next step is to explore more education cases and refining study outcome for an actual application.

Keywords: Multidisciplinary Design Education, Team Creativity, Multidisciplinary Factors and Conditions

INTRODUCTON

RESEARCH BACKGROUND

Development of Multidisciplinary Design Education
Role of Design is expanding from functional context to conceptual context. From simple division of product-, space-, visual- design, it has segmented into complex design divisions (ex. UX design, Interaction Design, etc). Furthermore, usage of Design generated a new dimension- the Design Thinking. Such expansion of Design usage provides useful tools for creative/innovative problem solving. Types and combination of multidisciplinary differed according to the needs of the times. Modern day's multidisciplinary keyword lies on design/design thinking multidisciplinary; like the way designers are educated to think is now perceived as particularly relevant to strategies in companies (Vogel, 2010), multidisciplinary design education(MDE) offers ability to successfully respond to complex social,

economical, technological changes. Synergy effect between various disciplines is also another expected merit.

But running MDE program does not automatically lead to enhancement of students' creative problem solving/thinking capability. This is why many pioneer design schools are strategically developing their MDE programs. Even simple study on some pioneer design school cases - i.e. Illinois Institute of Technology, Institute of Design, Stanford university, D-school, Aalto university, IDBM program - illustrates the fact that multidisciplinary design education can be specialized in various ways. These MDEs are managed hints that education dimensions (i.e. modules, staff member, facility, etc) can be developed into various strategies for MDE programs. To enable analysis of MDE dimensions, however, variables and conditions need to be defined and organized. This paper scrutinizes team projects in Seoul National University MDE program, organize factors and conditions into categories, and analyze the relationship (interaction) between the categories of a MDE model.

Integrated Creative Design Program

Seoul National University has started pilot MDE in 2009, and launched official program "Integrated Creative Design" in 2010 with governmental support (Inter-unified Design Educational Associates). The Integrated Creative Design program (ICD program) is an educational collaboration between product design, business administration, and mechanical & aerospace engineering departments.

Figure 1. Positioning of Integrated Creative Design

First two years of ICD program included many trials and errors. An interesting phenomena was that even under same professor and project process, the product or education quality outcome showed

differences in response to given conditions as familiarity of task subject, student composition, and class management method. This study particularly chose two project classes that clearly shows differences in response to various given conditions as analysis subject. Considering varying responses despite identical professor and creative process, the two projects are apt pilot study cases for the study purpose.

The two projects are: 'Future Mobile Life Research,' consist of 18 students from March to June 2010 and 'Future Home Life style Research,' consist of 15 students from September to December 2010. These were managed as multidisciplinary team based classes with students from three subjects- product design, business administration, and mechanical & aerospace engineering.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The research objective of this paper is to study MDE factors and conditions, organize into categories, and to build theory (model) that can be used to understand and improve MDE(multidisciplinary design education). The main goals are listed below;

- Organizing MDE influential factors and conditions into categories.
- Proposing MDE model though analysis of relation between defined categories.

This paper bases its study and deriving model on two industry-university cooperation projects of MDE program and thereby have limits which are as follows;

- Lack of variety in MDE cases.
- Absence of environmental and methodological guideline for MDE.
- Lack of study and theory on MDE.

To compensate the defects; this study focuses only on organizing factors and conditions into categories, and consents to counter influence the categories but does not specify interrelations.

Absence of environmental and methodological guideline for MDE is not only a defect to this paper, but a defect of MDE. In this study, academic studies and literatures on Creativity was taken as reference to compensate the defects.

To supplement the lack of theories on MDE, Grounded Theory Methodology was used as a study

method. Grounded Theory enables the analysis of phenomena. The methodology does not require specific norms or guidelines, and can deliver conclusion through inductive and deductive thinking.

Figure 2. Research process outline

CASES OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY DESIGN EDUCATION

Globally many design schools are operating multidisciplinary education offering various programs and disciplinary combination. In most representative MDE cases, schools are reinforced with different education dimension strengths. Following are three simple examples, design schools randomly select from BusinessWeek's selection of best design schools in 2009.

ILLINOIS INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, INSTITUTE OF DESIGN (U.S.): DUAL DEGREE ON DESIGN AND BUSINESS.

"IIT launched the two-year program in 2006 to offer two distinct degrees that tackle innovation. The design master's is overseen by the Institute of Design, and focuses on the link between strategy and human-centered innovation. The MBA, administered by IIT's Stuart School of Business, teaches a traditional AACSB-accredited business curriculum." (BusinessWeek, 2009)

Dual degree emphasizes equivalent importance in both design and business knowledge. In comparison to the D-school and IDBM, which offers minor studies programs, IIT specializes in excellence in both fields.

STANFORD UNIVERSITY, D-SCHOOL (U.S.): DESIGN-THINKING EDUCATION PROGRAM FOR STANFORD UNIVERSITY STUDENTS.

"Graduate students in the Joint Program in Design, which integrates technology and human-centered design, can join students from across Stanford University at the Hasso Plattner Institute of Design. ... About 350 students enroll each year and learn to use design methods to collaborate and solve problems." (BusinessWeek, 2009)

The D-school is open to only Stanford university students, meaning that the joint program is intended for non-design major students. The education program is built on industry-collaborative multidisciplinary team projects with design processes. The objective of D-school is cultivating 'design-thinkers' and not 'designers'.

AALTO UNIVERSITY, IDBM PROGRAM (FINLAND): COLLABORATIVE STUDY PROGRAM OF DESIGN, ENGINEERING, AND BUSINESS MAJORS.

"The IDBM minor studies program, started in 1995, represents 20 to 40 credits and allows students to take courses at the other participating schools. ... In addition, business, engineering, and design students work in multidisciplinary teams to learn how to manage international design-intensive businesses, operations, and product development." (BusinessWeek, 2009)

The IDBM program is different from IIT or D-school program in that the program is intended for students to learn how to use their skills/major in multidisciplinary teams. IDBM program is different from D-school program in that it focuses on growing design business management capability.

In these MDE cases, despite the successful trials and results, there isn't enough theoretical study or platform to understand MDE and to provide substantial feedback.

RESEARCH METHOD

METHOD FOR DATA COLLECTION

General information of the two multidisciplinary design education cases are as follows;

Project Title	Task	1. Topic 2. Target User 3. Outcome form
Future Mobile Life Research (Project A)	Developing Future Concept	1. Mobile Communication Device 2. 20 yrs-50 yrs 3. Scenario based presentation
Future Home Life style Research (Project B)	Developing Future Concept	1. Home & System Concept 2. 10 yrs-80 yrs 3. Scenario based presentation

Table 1. General information of the two project in Integrated Creative Design Program

Data collection protocols are made for effective data collection. Common traits are set to enable comparison between the two projects' Grounded Data. Grounded data were set to analyze the concepts of multidisciplinary design education.

Common traits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project objectives • Given time for the projects • Average academic level of students • Reward for achievement • Physical environment
Grounded data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student administration record • Professor & team director's record on student involvement • Record of each teams' meetings • Class Syllabus and knowledge resources • Students' work and activity outcomes • Class evaluation (done by students) • Survey and interview

Table 2. Data collection protocols

METHOD FOR DATA ANALYSIS

Strauss & Corbin's (1998) Grounded theory methodology was used for the analysis. Grounded Theory is a constant comparative method. In social sciences, it is known as one of systematic methodologies, emphasizing the generation of theory from data in the process of conducting research. It is mainly used for qualitative research, but is also applicable to other data (Glaser, 1967). In this paper, data analysis is processed in three steps: data sorting, open coding and axial coding.

- Open coding

Open coding is conceptualizing on the first level of abstraction. Written data from field notes or transcripts are conceptualized line by line. In the beginning of a study everything is coded in order

to find out about the problem and how it is being resolved. (Strauss A, Corbin J, 1990)

- Axial coding

Axial coding is a set of procedures whereby data are put back together in new ways after open coding, by making connections between categories. This phase proposes a coding paradigm that involved causal conditions, contextual conditions, intervening conditions, and action/interactional strategies. (Strauss A, Corbin J, 1990)

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

DATA SORTING

Tables and figures below are collected data, sorted according to Data Collection Protocols.

Case of Project A

	Team 1	Team 2	Team 3
Theme	Smart Consuming & Link-up Life	S-campus & Bubble	Two Lens & unidirectional Form
Student administration record	High Attendance	High Attendance	Fair Attendance
Professor & team director's record on student involvement	Divergent thinking, Need based approach, High dedication	Convergent thinking Experience & inspiration based approach, High dedication	Convergent thinking Concept based approach, High dedication
Record of each teams' meetings	Passive recording and communication	Passive recording and communication	Active recording and communication
Class Syllabus and Materials	Studied by not actively used	Actively Used by students	Not actively used but regularly followed
Students' work and activity outcomes	Good ideas, well developed, Low quality outcomes(done 60% by students)	Interesting Ideas, well developed, Low quality outcomes(done 80% by students)	Distinctive ideas, Slow developed, Low quality outcome(done 100% by students)
Class evaluation by students	Neutral	Positive	Positive

Table 3. Summary of collected data from project A

Figure 3. Still images of outcome in project A

Team 1	Team 2	Team 3
Team Director 2	Team Director 2	Team Director 2
Product design 4	Product design 4	Product design 3
Business administration 1	Business administration 1	Business administration 1
Mechanical & aerospace engineering 1	Mechanical & aerospace engineering 1	Mechanical & aerospace engineering 1
Ceramic craft 1		Metal craft 1

Table 4. Composition of team members in project A

Case of Project B

	Team 1	Team 2	Team 3
Theme	20-30 yrs	10 yrs & 40-60 yrs	70s-80s
Student administration record	Poor Attendance	High Attendance	Fair Attendance
Professor & team director's record on student involvement	Divergent thinking, needs based approach, Low dedication (changes to high dedication)	Divergent thinking, experience & inspiration based approach, High dedication	Convergent thinking, data based approach, Fair dedication
Record of each teams' meetings	Low recording and communication	Active recording and communication	Passive recording and communication
Class Syllabus and Materials	Not actively used but regularly followed	Actively Used by students	Studied by not actively used
Students' work and activity outcomes	Good ideas, Slow but well developed, Low quality outcomes (done 70% by students)	Interesting Ideas, stopped early but well developed, Low quality outcomes (done 100% by students)	Good ideas, lacked development, Low quality outcomes (done 80% by students)
Class evaluation by students	Neutral	Positive and Specific	Neutral

Table 5. Summary of collected data from project B

Figure 4. Still images of outcome in project B

Team 1	Team 2	Team 3
Team Director 1	Team Director 1	Team Director 1
Product design 1	Product design 1	Product design 1
Business administration 1	Business administration 1	Business administration 1
Mechanical & aerospace engineering 3	Mechanical & aerospace engineering 3	Mechanical & aerospace engineering 3

Table 6. Composition of team members in project B

Survey and interview result.

After the projects, simple survey and interview was held to find additional factors and conditions. In the survey and interviews, non-design school students were willing to dedicate with their professional knowledge. Also students with more MDE experience mentioned that the program had positive influence on their major studies as well.

OPEN CODING

After analyzing data from educational cases, common and distinctive elements were extracted, then extracted elements were processed into concepts. Similar concepts were grouped, and subcategorized. Finally, subcategories were re-categorized into Open Coding. As the result, 45 concepts, 14 subcategories and 4 categories were found.

Multidisciplinary Design Education		
-----Analysis Flow----->		
Concept	Subcategory	Category
Easy	Understanding of project topic	Project theme (topic) and attribution
Normal		
Complex		
Aesthetic	Attribution of project topic	
Functional		
Conceptual		
Passive	Project class/ team atmosphere	
Indifferent		
Attractive		
Active	Team type	
Group		
Group-Individual Hybrid		
Individual		
Graduate Level	Academic understanding of one's major	composition of project team members
Senior Level		
Junior Level		
Sophomore Level		
Single discipline : Design&Art fields	Diversity of disciplines	
Dual disciplines : Design&Art and Science&Engineering fields		
Multiple discipline : more than 3 fields		
Leading and important role	Involvement of design students	
Not leading but important role		
Not leading and general role		
Overall Management and maintenance.	Involvement of team director	
Participation on process and method		
Participation on process, method and context		
Participation on process, method, context and content		
Data/research based process	Process Attribution	project development process
Need/Experience based process		
Inspiration/concept based process		
In-class activity based ideation	Ideation Method	
Team discussion based ideation		
Individual task based ideation		

Liberal on Form of Outcome (UCC, story, etc...)	Design Development	
Constraint on Form of Outcome (mcook-up, rendering)		
No resulting outcome		
Closed resources: in-class text materials	Resource accessibility	knowledge resource management
Open resources: workshop, practices, field-trip, etc		
2D visualization ability	Visualization Ability	
3D visualization ability		
Space (environmental) visualization ability		
Mandatory education	Design Instruction	
Liberal education		
Design education		

Table 7. Open Coding Results

AXIAL CODING

This step defines the properties and the dimensions of Open Coding results. Then, each categories related with MDE phenomena are organized into four conditions (of the theory): causal conditions, contextual conditions, intervening conditions, and action/interactional strategies.

Causal Condition: composition of project team members

Multidisciplinary design education's foundation lies on composition of students from various disciplines. There is almost no adjustments made during the duration of class terms. It has most influence on class process, management and outcome.

Category	Subcategory	Property	Dimension
composition of project team members	Academic understanding of one's major	level	Sophomore ↔ Graduate
	Diversity of disciplines	scale	Number of variety
	Involvement of design students	attitude	Poor ↔ high
	Involvement of team director	essence	Involving context

Table 8. Properties and dimensions of causal condition (composition of project team members)

Intervening Condition: Knowledge resource management

Limits from composition of project team members can be supplemented through knowledge resource

management (various resources, tools, and coaching, etc).

Category	Subcategory	Property	Dimension
Knowledge resource management	Resource accessibility	essence	Open↔closed
	Visualization Ability	form	2D↔3D↔ expanded 3D
	Design Instruction	attitude	Forced↔liberal

Table 9. Properties and dimensions of intervening condition (knowledge resource management)

Contextual Condition: Project theme and attribution

Class objective and character are related to how the project should be managed and developed. Project theme and attribution is the core context that decides project development process.

Category	Subcategory	Property	Dimension
Project theme (topic) and attribution	understanding of project topic	level	Easy↔ Complex
	Attribution of project topic	essence	Aesthetic↔ Functional↔ Conceptual
	Project class/team atmosphere	attitude	Passive↔ Active
	Team type	scale	Group↔ Individual

Table 10. Properties and dimensions of contextual condition (project theme and attribution)

Action/Interaction Strategies: Project development process

Project development process interacts with teams and individuals, and thereby influences class directions and outcomes.

Category	Subcategory	Property	Dimension
Project development process	Process Attribution	essence	data↔need↔in spiration
	Ideation Method	scale	private↔team ↔class
	Design Development	form	Productive↔ not productive

Table 11. Properties and dimensions of contextual condition (project theme and attribution)

DISCUSSIONS: FACTORS AND CONDITIONS OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY DESIGN EDUCATION

Composition of project team members

- Academic understanding of one’s major

When the students’ understanding of the subject did not meet the expected level, multidisciplinary composition was rather a disturbance factor. Stronger synergy effect was apparent in team cases with more professionally skilled students.
- Diversity of disciplines

When the disciplinary diversity reached the tipping point, students showed lower concentration during the process. This matter of concentration was, however, controllable by team director.

- Involvement of design students

Better ideas and outcomes were produced when design school students’ ratio (verses non-design students) and involvement were high. However, excessive percentage of design school students’ participation dropped non-design major students’ motivation.

- Involvement of team director.

Team director plays essential role in leading multidisciplinary students to reach the project goal. The comprehension of skills and results differed according to team-directors’ attributes. The cause seems to be from the differences in the leadership (collaborative skills) and the understanding of the subject matter of the team-directors. Each teams showed strength in coherence with the mentor’s expertise.

Knowledge resource management

- Resource accessibility

Open resource accessibility was, according to students, beneficial. In cases of low design student involvement- i.e. Project B- workshop, field-trip and special seminars were useful supplementary resources.
- Visualization ability

Visualization and rapid prototyping enabled better communication between various disciplines.

- Design instruction

During the projects, design instructions were constantly mentioned on regularly basis by team directors and professor. Especially in cases of low design students’ involvement, positive results were generated from design education.

Project theme and attribution

- Understanding of project topic

When dealing with familiar subjects, generated ideas showed the tendency of either ‘imagination lacking reality’ or ‘ideas within biased boundary.’ On the other hand, when the project topic was unfamiliar, students showed low understanding of users. When target users property corresponded that of the students, they showed better understanding of the topic and the users. Better understanding, however, did not always lead to good result.
- Attribution of project topic

With project topic where styling was important, multidisciplinary education did not have much contribution. It was functional or conceptual topic that multidisciplinary created positive effect.

Also, students showed higher interest when topic showed relevances to diverse fields. Students’ were motivated to use their professional knowledge. Such result underlines the importance of accordance in disciplines, topics, methods and processes.

- Project class/team atmosphere

Overall atmosphere and attitude influences the class flow and quality. This variable can be controlled by environmental change, stirring topics and goals, and stimulating with events (i.e. workshop).
- Team type

In individual tasks, collaborative effect was seldom seen. The occurrence of the effect could however be made active through vibrant discussion and brain storming.

Project development process

- Process attribution

Students generally favored Inspiration/concept based processes, but were against data/research based process. However, such reaction had little impact since the process attribution and project topic were more influential.

- Ideation Method

Each team showed different approaches to ideation methods and processes. This created the difference in quality of idea and communication. Involvement of design students
- Design Development

During the ideation and concept development process, all students showed high degree of involvement and positive productivity. In the final phase of the process, however, design students had more workload. On the other hand, other disciplinary students found difficulty in finding contributory tasks. When the shape of the final product was liberal, the unbalance of final phase workload was lesser than that of constrained.

CONCLUSIONS

A MODEL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY DESIGN EDUCATION

Model below is the flow chart of the casual model of multidisciplinary design education (which was identified in axial coding).

Figure 5. A Causal model of multidisciplinary design education

- MDE phenomenon has its foundation on Composition of project team members. The composition of professional-level, discipline and attribution of students are the core factors of learning and outcome.

- Limits and challenges from multidisciplinary team composition can be supplemented with adequate management of knowledge resources.
- Higher correspondence between project theme, attribution and team composition creates better deliverance of MDE potential.
- Project development process is a strategy which students, team, education environment and curriculum generates outcome. Flexible processing with constant feedback leads to better results.

NEXT RESEARCH PLAN

This study is the conclusion drawn from two MDE project cases. Therefore, the evidential data collected may be insufficient. Although the limitation was supplemented with studies from other educational cases and research, the paper still lacks persuasiveness in explanation of conditions, variables and the relations of the two.

Therefore, the first future plan of the research is to take complementary measure, and thereby refining the study outcome. Next plan is to implement the study outcome into multidisciplinary design education practices. Further exploration of relating

academic papers - i.e. team creativity, educational methodology - would also provide insights for a further research.

REFERENCES

- Belbin, R. M. (1991) Design Innovation and the TEAM. Design Management Journal. 2(3), p38-42
- Glaser BG, Strauss A. (1967) Discovery of Grounded Theory. Strategies for Qualitative Research. Sociology Press
- Glaser BG (ed). (1993) Examples of Grounded Theory: A Reader. Sociology Press.
- Jantsch, E. (1970) Towards Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary in Education and Innovation. 106
- KDRI. (2008) Creativity through convergence. IDCC 2008 Proceedings. Chapter II.
- Lockwood, T. (ed). (2010). Design Thinking; integrating innovation, customer experience, and brand value. Allworth Press. NY. P.4.
- Oh Younghak. (2010) Roll of Coordinator in Design-Oriented Multidisciplinary Class.
- Robert J. Sternberg. (2006) The Nature of Creativity, Creativity Research Journal 2006, Vol. 18, No. 1, p. 87-98
- Runco, M.A. (2009) Creativity theories and themes: research, development, and practice (Trans.) Seoul: Elseviser Korea L.L.C with Sigma Press
- Siau, K. L. (1995) Group Creativity and Technology. Journal of Creative Behavior. 29(3). p201-216.
- Strauss A, Corbin J. (1990) Basics of Qualitative Research: Grounded Theory Procedures and Techniques. Sage. 90-96
- http://www.businessweek.com/interactive_reports/dschools_2009.html (article. World's Best Design Programs)